

The Mediating Effect of Technostress on the Relationship Between Metacognition and Blended Learning Engagement of Students in Mathematics in the Modern World

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Abstract

This study aims to identify the mediating effect of technostress on the relationship between metacognition and blended learning engagement of students in mathematics in the modern world. The researcher utilized a non-experimental quantitative design using the descriptive-correlational approach with mediating effect analysis. A sample of 100 participants was chosen through a simple random sampling technique. The study reveals a high level manifested of both metacognition and blended learning engagement, while also indicating a high level of technostress among students in mathematics in the modern world. There is a significant relationship between metacognition and blended learning engagement, metacognition and the technostress, and technostress and the blended learning engagement of students. The result shows that there is a full mediating effect of Technostress on the relationship between Metacognition and Blended learning engagement of students of Mathematics in the Modern World. There is also an indirect effect of technostress on the blended learning engagement of students in mathematics in the modern world. Moreover, the presence of metacognition has a beneficial influence on the engagement of students in blended learning as it assists them in effectively navigating both online and offline learning, setting objectives, tracking their progress, and adapting strategies accordingly. Metacognition enables self-regulated learning, resulting in heightened engagement and achievement. Lastly, it is crucial to promote students' adeptness in managing the ever-changing landscape of computer hardware, staying updated, establishing a refresh cycle, prioritizing compatibility, offering comprehensive training and documentation, considering outsourcing if needed, and diligently monitoring performance.

Keywords: *Technostress, metacognition, blended learning engagement, college students, mathematics in the modern world, Davao City, Philippines.*

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Introduction

In the contemporary era, pervasive and limitless technology updates induce technostress among individuals, impacting students navigating blended learning environments that integrate traditional and technological tools. While some adapt to online education, others face stress, particularly in subjects like mathematics, where technostress hinders metacognition (Broadbent, 2017; Oladosu Alasan et al., 2020; Kramarski, Weiss, & Kololshi-Minsker, 2014). Implementing blended learning globally poses challenges, including increased effort, time commitment, and difficulty balancing face-to-face and online learning (Alvarez, 2020). Metacognition's role is crucial, but its development proves challenging for many students, impacting academic performance (Lakhal, 2021). In Leyte, Philippines, children's struggles with the new online learning setting affect their physical, emotional, and financial well-being, causing a sense of disconnection among students (Ayub, 2022). Discussions in Tagum, Philippines, reveal that metacognitive judgments impact students' psychological well-being, while in Davao, Philippines, stress arises from attempts to cope with rapidly changing ICTs (Norman, 2020). Technological stress, observed in Bukidnon, Philippines, contributes to work overload and dissatisfaction (Tarafdar et al., 2016). This study addresses the mediating effect of technostress on the relationship between metacognition and blended learning engagement, emphasizing the urgency of research to enlighten students about the modern world's challenges in mathematics education. The absence of prior research intensifies the need for this study to fill existing knowledge gaps

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the respondents' level of mediating effects of technostress on the relationship between Metacognition and Blended Learning Engagements of students in mathematics in the modern world academic year 2022-2023. To be more specific, this study aims to answer the following;

1. Is there a significant relationship between Metacognition and Blended Learning Engagement of the students in Mathematics in the Modern World?
2. Is there a significant relationship between Metacognition and Technostress?
3. Is there a significant relationship between technostress and blended learning of the students in Mathematics in the Modern World?
4. Is there a significant mediating effect of technostress on the relationship between Metacognition and learning engagement of Mathematics in the Modern World students?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses will be tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H_{01} : There is no significant relationship between Metacognition and blended learning engagement of Mathematics in the Modern World students.

H_{02} : There is no significant relationship between Metacognition and Technostress of Mathematics in the Modern World Students

H_{03} : There is no significant relationship between technostress and blended learning of the students in Mathematics in the Modern World.

H_{04} : There is no significant mediating effect of technostress on the relationship between Metacognition and learning engagement of Mathematics in the Modern World students.

Methods

This research utilized a non-experimental quantitative design using a descriptive-correlational approach with mediating effect analysis. The study was conducted in Davao City, Philippines, offering Mathematics in the Modern World Subject. Due to its ranking as the second most competitive highly-urbanized city in 2020, it was observed in Davao City that students' metacognition in math had poor performance and the achievement of the students was very low, which caused stress towards the students, affecting their performance in math. The researchers took at least 100 respondents, preferably the 1st year students from the institution. The researchers used survey questionnaires for the respondents. A questionnaire was a research instrument composed of a list of questions for the respondents. Upon conducting this study, the researchers observed specific ethical guidelines. The ethical guidelines that the researcher uses are from Philippine Health Research Ethics Board's National Ethical Guidelines for Health and Health-Related Research. The researchers used Pearson-R and Mediating Analysis.

Results and Discussions

SOP 1: Is there a significant relationship between Metacognition and Blended Learning Engagement of the students in Mathematics in the Modern World?

Table 1. Significance of the Relationship between Metacognition and Blended Learning Engagement of Students in Mathematics in the Modern World

Metacognition	Blended Learning Engagement			
	r	p-value	Decision on H_0	Interpretation
	.277	.005	Reject	Significant

As shown in the table above, there is a significant relationship between metacognition and blended learning engagement of students of mathematics in the modern world ($p=.005 < 0.05$). Looking at the r-value of 0.277, this means that there is a negligible correlation between metacognition and blended learning engagement of the student in mathematics in the modern world. It implies that as metacognition increases, then blended learning engagement increases also, and vice versa.

The result implies that math teachers may also find a way to increase metacognition by explicitly teaching students strategies for planning, monitoring, and evaluating their own learning. Math teachers can provide regular opportunities for students to reflect on their learning experiences and offer constructive feedback that focuses on students' metacognitive processes as well as their content knowledge to exercise their problem-solving skills and critical thinking in solving a math problem. It is important to

highlight their strengths, suggest areas for improvement, and provide guidance on how to enhance their learning strategies to continue learning math lessons.

Technology advances have led to a shift from traditional teaching methods to online blended learning. Education reforms aim to address disparities in mathematics performance, but frustration with blended learning may negatively impact students' academic self-efficacy and effort (Fulgencio, 2021). According to some studies, metacognition-based mathematics instruction should be planned to improve the processes of monitoring and regulating students' mathematical thinking when solving problems (Seker & Engin, 2018; Alzahrani, 2017). Furthermore, Cognitive self-consciousness improves decision-making, exam performance, and self-esteem, and speeds up the learning process (Leutwyler, 2019).

SOP 2: Is there a significant relationship between Metacognition and Technostress?

Table 2. Significance on the Relationship between Metacognition and Technostress of Students in Mathematics in the Modern World

Metacognition	Technostress			
	r	p-value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
	.470	.000	Reject	Significant

As shown in the table above, the test indicated that there is a significant relationship between metacognition and technostress ($p=.000 < 0.05$). Looking at the r-value of 0.470, this means that there is a low positive correlation between students in mathematics in the modern world subject. This also means that the null hypothesis will be rejected and there is a significant relationship. This also concludes that as the metacognition increases then the technostress increases as well.

The result implies that math teachers may find a way to help students by promoting Techno-comfort (Technostress) in the class. Math teachers can teach students to approach technology use in a more intentional and mindful way. They can develop digital literacy skills, such as evaluating online problem-solving, navigating digital tools effectively that will help them with their mathematics subject, and using technology as a tool for learning more about mathematics. This cultivates critical thinking skills necessary for success in the digital age.

Online instruction is flexible and provides more students with opportunities to access high-quality learning. Because of this new delivery method students significantly rely on information and communication technologies (ICTs) for both education and communication (Huber & Helm, 2020). Students experience difficulties such as limited knowledge about technology and some technical issues (Laspinas, 2015). However, several studies have discovered that some technological stressors unexpectedly have no adverse effects or even have beneficial impacts on people (Califf & Brooks, 2020). Lazarus' transactional theory of stress explains how individuals react to stress, highlighting coping and assessment processes influencing how stressors affect them. It shows that technostress can be perceived as a challenge or threat, which has a diverse effect on students' metacognition. (Wang & Yao, 2021).

SOP 3: Is there a significant relationship between technostress and blended learning of the students in Mathematics in the Modern World?

Table 3. Significance on the Relationship between Technostress and Blended Learning Engagement of Students in Mathematics in the Modern World

Technostress	Blended Learning Engagement			
	r	p-value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
	.572	.000	Reject	Significant

As presented in the table above, the result of this test indicated that there is a significant relationship between Blended Learning Engagement and Technostress ($p = .000 < .05$). Looking at the r-value of 0.572, this means that there is a moderate positive correlation between Blended Learning Engagement and Technostress of students of mathematics in the modern world. Also, the table shows that the null hypothesis will be rejected and the interpretation is significant. The test also indicates that if the Blended Learning Engagement increases, the techno comfort (technostress) will also increase, and vice versa.

The result implies that math teachers may also find a way to help students on how to perform well in the blended learning engagement of students in mathematics in the modern world. Math teachers may give students more time to work on their math activities to avoid stress for the students. Also, teachers can also rely on traditional instructional methods, such as textbooks and in-person lectures. The flexibility of blended learning allows students to personalize their learning experience, accommodating different learning styles and preferences. Moreover, the integration of technology fosters a sense of digital literacy and enhances critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

Traditional instruction methods cause student frustration, leading to incomplete work activities and poor assessment performance. The abrupt transition to technology-enhanced learning has resulted in work overload for students, requiring more time and effort (Fulgencio, 2021). Additionally, techno-stress among students at universities may be linked to burnout, lowered performance, decreased learning engagement, and withdrawal from technology-enhanced learning (Qi, 2019). However, some study explains that educators must suggest problem-solving-based tests during or after a synchronous meeting. Instructors reported that integrating academic material with professional practice will increase students' emotional and cognitive involvement (Bond & Bedenlier, 2019). This method will promote student engagement through asynchronous activities and knowledge deepening during synchronous meetings (Jeffrey et al., 2014).

SOP 4: Is there a significant mediating effect of technostress on the relationship between Metacognition and learning engagement of Mathematics in the Modern World students?

Table 4. Path Coefficients on the Mediating Effect of Technostress on the Relationship between Metacognition and Blended Learning Engagement of students in Mathematics in the Modern World

			Estimate	Std. Error	p-val	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Technostress	→	Blended Learning Engagement	0.871	0.143	0.000	Reject	Significant
Metacognition	→	Blended Learning Engagement	0.020	0.174	0.907	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
Metacognition	→	Technostress	0.574	0.108	0.000	Reject	Significant

As shown in the table, the effect of technostress on blended learning engagement has an estimated value of 0.871, standard error of 0.143, and a p-value of <0.01 . This means that there is a significant effect of technostress on the blended learning of students in Mathematics in the Modern World. Moreover, the effect of metacognition on technostress has an estimated value of 0.574, a standard error of 0.174, and a p-value of <0.01 . This means that there is a significant effect of Metacognition on the technostress of students in mathematics in the modern world. there is a 0.574 unit increase in the effect of metacognition on technostress. Overall, there is a full mediating effect of technostress on the relationship between metacognition and blended learning engagement of students in mathematics in the modern world. It is shown in the path analysis below:

Figure 1: Path Analysis on the Mediating Effect of Technostress on the Relationship between Metacognition and Blended Learning Engagement of Students in Mathematics in the Modern World

Moreover, there is a full mediating effect of Technostress on Metacognition and Blended Learning Engagement of Students in Mathematics in the Modern World. Increased metacognition leads to higher levels of technostress. Furthermore, technostress has a significant impact on blended learning engagement, as an increase in blended learning corresponds to an increase in technostress. However, there is no significant effect of metacognition on blended learning engagement because a high level of metacognition will help students cope with blended learning engagement.

The study aligns with Piaget's Cognitive learning theory (1936), emphasizing the significance of understanding thought processes in learning to enhance knowledge acquisition. Piaget's theory suggests that manipulating internal and external factors impacting thinking can improve learning efficiency. In the context of the research, this is reflected in the role of metacognition in mediating technostress and influencing blended learning engagement for students in mathematics. The cognitive learning

process, particularly in math education within a blended learning environment, involves associating new information with existing knowledge.

Conclusion

The study reveals that students in the Mathematics in the Modern World course exhibit confidence in their memory, employ coping mechanisms to manage task-related worries and demonstrate effective time management skills. They appreciate the use of modern tools in blended learning, benefit from technology for flexible learning, and actively stay updated on new features. Teachers can enhance metacognition by teaching student's strategies for planning, monitoring, and evaluating their learning. Balancing technology usage and incorporating traditional instructional methods can prevent technostress and its negative impact on metacognitive abilities. Overall, metacognition positively impacts blended learning engagement by helping students navigate learning, set goals, monitor progress, and adjust strategies, leading to increased success. In addition, the integration of online resources, interactive activities, and student engagement in blended learning has the potential to greatly enhance mathematical education at the university level. By utilizing these tools, students can develop a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts and apply them in real-world contexts. Furthermore, the active involvement of students in blended learning fosters a sense of ownership and empowerment in their educational journey, leading to higher levels of motivation and engagement.

Recommendations

In order to support students in diverse learning modalities, school administrators should implement policies and guidelines centered on students' needs, ensuring access to a user-friendly and secure educational platform. The objectives should prioritize a flexible and engaging learning experience to accommodate diverse needs, with a focus on addressing challenges in blended learning through seminars and informing students about digital tools. Mathematics instructors, within this framework, play a crucial role in designing blended learning experiences that foster interactivity and critical thinking, guiding students to become technologically literate. Encouraging a carefree mindset and embracing blended learning opportunities are essential for students to excel, while instructors should prioritize professional growth in teaching mathematics. To mitigate technostress, students must adeptly manage technological changes, stay informed, prioritize compatibility, and receive comprehensive training. The study serves as a foundation for future research, suggesting investigations into strategies for educators to enhance learning outcomes and develop essential technology-related skills.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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